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Correlating the Gender wise Institutional Climate of Teacher Educators with their Professional Commitment: An analytical study in the light of New Education Policy 2020

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Abstract : The study aims to correlate the institutional climate of teacher educators as per the gender with their professional commitment. The study employed a random sample of 543 teacher educators consisting of 162 males and 381 females for the purpose of obtaining the gender wise score on the institutional climate and the professional commitment as well. The sample size included teacher educators from each type of the education college, i.e. government, government-aided and private (self-financed) one that are running in Punjab. The scale developed by Kanchan Kohli (2005) to measure the professional commitment and that by S. P. Anand (1994), namely Teacher Training College Climate Inventory to measure the institutional climate were used as appropriate tools to collect the data. The data analyzed using the Microsoft Excel highlights a significant and positive correlation for both the variables- institutional climate and professional commitment in each case taken up either for male teacher educators or for female teacher educators. The study was planned and executed in the right vibes of principles, guidelines and recommendations of the New Education Policy 2020 that advocate running of well equipped institutions with basic infrastructure and facilities for higher education having highly motivated, energized, capable and engaged faculty. Further, this study tends to incorporate the vision for fostering a sound and congenial work/service-environment and culture in an education institution as held by the policy. The study finds its implication in terms of inspiring and motivating the concerned stakeholders, regulatory bodies and controlling authorities to ensure that institutions function qualitatively to impart education on a holistic and multidisciplinary pattern; this is indeed what is required in modern times.

Keywords : Teacher Educators, Institutional Climate, Professional Commitment, Teacher-Education Institutions, Higher Education, Service Environment.

Introduction

True indeed, it is education that leads to the social development of an individual. Learning, i.e. receiving education is an ongoing process that continues lifelong. It is education that brings about one's behavioral transformation. Besides, it helps an individual to acquire knowledge and skill for having successful existence with capability to secure good livelihood. Undoubtedly, education prepares effective citizens for the future who may serve the society and nation well. Self-confident and promising citizens with healthy life mottos are likely to be turned out by teachers of quality alone. Such proficient and dedicated teachers of quality are prepared by teacher educators who serve in teacher-training institutes. That is how the significant role of a teacher educator claims to be paramount as he/she is held responsible for producing dynamic, energetic and committed school teachers who may handle beginners/learners effectively and lead them in the right direction.

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It is right to conclude with a broad vision that teacher educators who deal with prospective school teachers must be highly learned and professionally skilled and committed with a high degree of expertise. To the utmost surprise, it has been observed so far that a lot many teacher educators particularly those working in private institutions lack qualification, knowledge, skill, ability and commitment, required to work in a teacher training institute as an eligible and competent faculty-member. This comment is supported by several reports on inspections of education colleges, conducted till now by regulatory and controlling bodies. This problem has been featured as a challenging issue by the NEP 2020 to be addressed in the pursuit of achieving the goals of higher education. The policy takes into account the sub-standard quality of functioning of teacher training colleges and utter lack of professionalism on part of the working teacher educators as the main challenging issues to be resolved.

The NEP 2020 makes strong recommendation for concrete measures to be taken to ensure that every institution functions with an academic environment of optimum quality supported by the adequate infrastructure that stimulates the smooth teaching-learning process bringing out the desirable outcome. The policy lays emphasis on the need for renovating the service environment and culture of educational institutions to make the same secure and agreeable with the goal to raise the ability of teachers at an optimum level to make them effective to perform their jobs, and to ensure that they constitute an integral part of a large and welfare caring community which includes students, parents, all other faculty members and support staff if any.

Finally, it may be summarized very well, in terms of concluding remarks, that the institutional climate as perceived by teacher educators influences their professional commitment directly. Quality of the institutional climate of teacher educators and their commitment, both these factors determine how the academic environment functions at an institution. In fact, an institutional climate of high order characterized by good administration and management, proper discipline, group cohesion, best possible infrastructure, availability of common facilities and opportunity for the professional excellence provides a suitable platform for enhancement of job satisfaction and commitment of teacher educators. Of course, this leads to a positive outcome in terms of producing prospective school teachers of quality. Speaking precisely, the positive climate and conducive work culture of an institution invigorates the teaching-learning process with the best outcome. The concerned regulatory and controlling bodies/authorities are supposed to monitor and govern the functioning of teacher-education institutions on the lines as focussed here. This all motivates the researcher to undertake the study of gender wise institutional climate of teacher educators in relation to their professional commitment.

Review of the Related Literature

Smith (2009) made an investigation of school climate and commitment of elementary school teachers of North East Alabama and concluded that there was positive and significant relationship with teacher commitment and school climate.

Danish et al. (2015) studied impact of organizational climate on job satisfaction and organizational commitment of 179 college & university teachers. Their findings revealed that organizational climate influenced commitment & job satisfaction of their said subjects.

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Goswami and Choudhury (2016) studied professional commitment of teacher educators with regard to institutional climate and came out with the result that there is significant relation between commitment level and institutional climate of B. Ed. teacher educators.

Khan (2019) investigated the impact of organizational climate on teachers' commitment with a sample of 230 elementary private school teachers and concluded that there exists significant and positive relationship between overall school climate and teachers' commitment.

Chung (2020) investigated the organizational climate and teachers' commitment of 375 secondary school teachers in Sarawak (Malaysia) and found a strong and positive correlation with the commitment and the organizational climate dimensions, i.e. collegial leadership, teacher professionalism and academic press.

Zain and Shaffie (2023) studied the relationship between school organizational climate and teachers' commitment among Malaysian school teachers and found came out with the findings that moderate strong relationship between school organizational climate and teachers' commitment.

Chanu and Shantikumar (2023) studied the impact of organizational climate on the professional commitment of teacher educators in Manipur. Finding indicated that professional commitment of teacher educators was strongly influenced by their job place environment and not necessarily by demographic aspects, i.e. gender of teachers, their experience, etc. The study gives suggestions in terms of emphasizing on the promotion of congenial institutional climate which may boost the satisfaction and motivation of teachers and provide professional development opportunities for quality teacher preparation at teacher training colleges in Manipur.

Sanchez (2022) aimed to study as to whether employees work engagement mediates the relationship between professional commitment and organizational climate? As per the result, positive and significant correlation existed between professional commitment and organizational climate. Again, work engagement of employees was influenced by the institutional climate considerably.

Gonzales and Diaso (2024) investigated school climate and teachers' commitment among 134 teachers of Monkayo West District. The study concluded that commitment was not affected by school climate.

Objectives of the Study

- (1) To study the relationship between institutional climate and professional commitment of male teacher educators.
- (2) To study the relationship between institutional climate and professional commitment of female teacher educators.

Hypotheses of the Study: The objective wise null hypotheses were framed in the following manner:

1. There does not exist any significant relationship between institutional climate and professional commitment of male teacher educators.
2. There does not exist any significant relationship between institutional climate and professional commitment of female teacher educators.

Data-Collection: Based on the survey conducted through questionnaires that were administered on the faculty of a good many education colleges affiliated to Punjabi university, Patiala, Panjab University, Chandigarh & Guru Nanak Dev University,

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Amritsar (all functioning in Punjab), a sample comprising 162 male teacher educators & 381 female teacher educators was formed randomly for purpose of the study. Selection of these colleges included all the three types, i.e. government, government-aided & self-financed private ones that run in Punjab.

Research-Method: The study was performed by making descriptive research approach that required the use of quantitative method. Selection of research-tools included: (i) Scale for Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators developed by Kanchan Kohli (2005) and (ii) Teacher Training College Climate Inventory constructed by S. P. Anand (1994) to measure the institutional climate of teacher educators.

Data Analysis and Interpretation: Analysis for determining the degree of relationship between institutional climate and professional commitment of teacher educators was done by applying the Karl Pearson's product moment method, whereby the value of correlation coefficient (Pearson's r) was obtained. This is all shown gender wise in table-1 and table-2 given below.

Table 1

Statistical analysis for correlation between institutional climate and professional commitment of male teacher educators

Variable	Mean score	Standard Deviation	No. of male teacher educators	Sum of Products	Pearson's r
Institutional climate	270.969	65.522	162	4564854	0.316**
Professional commitment	103.043	12.486			
**p < 0.01					

It is evident from the table 1 that the value of Pearson's r that shows extent of correlation between institutional climate and professional commitment is 0.316. This value is greater than the table value 0.11 for significance at 0.01 level and 160 degree of freedom. This means clearly that a significant and positive relationship exists between institutional climate and professional commitment of male teacher educators. As such, statement of the null hypothesis that "There does not exist any significant relationship between institutional climate and professional commitment of male teacher educators", is rejected straight way.

Table 2

Statistical analysis for correlation between institutional climate and professional commitment of female teacher educators

Variable	Mean score	Standard Deviation	No. of female teacher educators	Sum of Products	Pearson's r
Institutional climate	288.079	60.276	381	11143034	0.294**
Professional commitment	100.759	12.466			
**p < 0.01					

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The table no. 2 reveals that the value of correlation coefficient (r) that assesses the significance of interrelationship in respect of institutional climate and professional commitment of female teacher educators is 0.294. This obtained value of ' r ' is higher than the table value 0.11 at 0.01 level of significance and for 379 degree of freedom. This makes it obvious that institutional climate of female teacher educators bears a significant and positive correlation with their professional commitment. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated as: "There does not exist any significant relationship between institutional climate and professional commitment of female teacher educators", goes unaccepted.

Result and Discussion

Findings of the study project largely how the institutional climate and professional commitment of teacher educators either males or females are interrelated showing a significant and positive correlation; meaning thereby better is the quality of institutional climate, higher is the degree of professional commitment of male or female teacher educators. The reason underlying this result of the study may be stated as most of the education colleges provide good institutional climate and availability of the proper infrastructure and facility. Such a supportive institutional climate is likely to be marked with a favourable work environment. This, of course, goes a long way to motivate the teacher educators to do the job with commitment. The finding of this current research-study goes in line with that of each one of studies conducted earlier by Smith (2009), Danish et al. (2015), Goswami and Choudhury (2016), Khan (2019), Chung (2020), Sanchez (2022), Chanu and Santikumar (2023), Zain and Shaffiee (2023) who underscore very well a significant and positive correlation in respect of interconnection between professional commitment and institutional climate of teachers. However, the finding of the present research goes anti-parallel to that of the study accomplished by Gonzales and Diaso (2024) who arrive at the result that commitment of teachers remains unaffected by the school climate.

Implication of the Study

Findings of the study make it imperative to ensure that the institutional climate of any education-college functions well in terms of maintaining the good discipline, developing the healthy relationship between teacher and taught, encouraging team spirit to strike any job related task in cohesion with collaborative effort, making the supporting contribution to the overall work environment by the entire faculty and providing accessibility to the requisite infrastructure & facility. Inevitably, such a type of institutional climate of quality makes it all possible for motivation, capability and commitment of teacher educators to go well. This, all together, leads one to infer that a huge liability lies on the part of stakeholders and agencies/authorities concerned to monitor and regulate the functioning of any education-college within qualitative parameters as defined in the foregoing lines for the sake of making the institutional climate good enough for teacher educators to work with zeal and commitment. All the suggestions given here in terms of implication of the study are substantiated by the provision for the implementation of principles, initiatives, strategies as laid down in the text of NEP 2020 under definite guidelines in respect of the higher teacher – education at a formal level for the sole purpose to raise well qualified, energized, proficient and committed faculty that is capable to produce future school

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teachers of quality in the true sense. Needless to say, only such teachers are expected to play a vital role in the nation building.

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